

The Influence of Interpersonal Needs on Collaborative Learning Efforts during Participation in Group Assignments and Projects amongst Limkokwing University Students in Botswana

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the influence of Interpersonal Needs on Collaborative Learning Efforts during Participation in Group Assignments and Projects amongst Limkokwing University of Creative Technology students in Botswana. The Fundamental Interpersonal Relationship Orientation - Behaviour (FIRO-B) model was used to determine the extent to which students at Limkokwing University of Creative Technology collaborate during learning. The FIRO-B questionnaire instrument was distributed to 50 student-respondents who were randomly selected. SPSS was used to analyse the data using Descriptive Statistics (Mean and Standard Deviation). The results of the study revealed that Limkokwing University of Creative Technology students have high levels of interpersonal needs rated at (39 - 54) FIRO-B scores. Results indicated that students enjoyed engaging in collaborative learning in all areas of Inclusion, Control and Affection.

Keywords: *Fundamental Interpersonal Relationship Orientation- Behaviour (FIRO-B); Students; Collaborative Learning ; Inclusion; Control; Affection; Expressed Behavior; Wanted Behaviour.*

Introduction

Johnson & Johnson (1999) defined collaborative learning as teaching and learning approaches and strategies that seek to promote the spirit of working together amongst students during the learning process. However, Baker and Clark (2010) described Collaborative learning as teaching and learning educational methodologies that comprise groups of students who are working together to solve a problem, complete a task, or create a product.

Peer learning or teaching is one of the collaborative learning activities which involve students discussing some concepts to find solutions to problems at hand in pairs or small groups. This as stated by Galton, Hargreaves and Pell (2009) is similar to the idea that two or three heads are better than one. As a result, educational researchers have found that through peer instruction, students teach each other by addressing misinterpretations and clarifying misconceptions (Galton et al., 2009). Therefore, during collaborative learning, students discuss in small manageable groups and are able to work on a particular problem with the aim of reaching a common and suitable solution (Baker & Clark, 2010).

The collaborative learning approaches as indicated by Nguyen, Terlouw and Pilot (2012) are fostered towards optimizing students' own learning and the learning of others. Moreover, research reveals that teachers in both primary and secondary levels of education have tried various types of collaborative activities in their classrooms and have been successful in improving their students' results (Iloanya, 2014). However, there are limited studies about the use of the strategies at the university levels particularly in developing Southern Africa, including Botswana (Ramatlapana & Vlaardingerbroek, 2001). As stated by Ramatlapana and Vlaardingerbroek (2001) there is need to move from the traditional teaching methods to the student-centered learning methods which involve collaborative learning.

Collaborative learning in the university environment according to La Rocca, Margottini and Capobianco (2014) has been realised to likely influence students to maintain some constant motivation and affection towards their studies. The international literature reveals that the practice of collaborative learning amongst the tertiary students have produced significant results as it helps them to interact with their peers, thereby

improving their understanding of what they learn (Chiriac & Granström, 2012; La Rocca et al., 2014). Similar studies by Slavin (1996) and Ha Le, Janssen & Wubbels (2018) found out that collaborative learning effort during teaching and learning improved academic achievement amongst university learners.

Collaborative learning activities enable the learners to engage in challenging tasks or questions (Galton et al., 2009). Rather than beginning with facts and ideas and then moving to applications, Galton et al. (2009) collaborative learning activities often begin with problems, for which students must clarify relevant facts, ideas and solutions. Instead of engaging in observations of questions and answers, or problems and solutions, students also develop their critical thinking and reasoning skills (Galton et al., 2009).

Research further shows that learning experiences that are active, social, contextual, engaging, and student-centered lead to meaningful learning (Ha Le et al., 2018). The benefits of collaborative learning include: Exposure to and an increase in understanding of various viewpoints; Development of higher-level critical thinking, oral communication, self-management, and leadership skills (Ha Le et al., 2018).

This paper evaluated students need for: inclusion, control and affection behaviours during collaborative learning amongst Limkokwing University of Creative Technology students in Botswana.

Statement of the problem

When evaluating the success of collaborative learning, various researchers have found different types of challenges that hinder the successful implementation and application of collaborative learning by teachers and lecturers in their classrooms (Greenacre, 2010). Some of the notable challenges identified by Blatchford, Kutnick, Baines & Galton (2003) include: (1) Unequal participation in group assignments and major projects (2) Lack of communication (3) Poor interpersonal skills (4) and most importantly, lack of collaborative skills amongst learners. However, collaborative learning has several benefits which should not be overlooked. Some of the benefits outlined include; Development of self-management and leadership skills; Improvement of knowledge acquisition and retention; Promotion of learning from other's view points; Improvement of critical thinking and reasoning; Development of public speaking and active listening; and the promotion of listening to criticism and advice from others (Blatchford et al., 2003).

These challenges and benefits have been observed and experienced by some of the lecturers and learners at Limkokwing University of Creative Technology. Therefore, this paper is set out to provide workable solutions to the challenges faced by Limkokwing University of Creative Technology lecturers and learners towards improving their collaborationskills, which would beneficially improve the academic performance of learners.

Research objectives

This paper was driven by the following research objectives:

- To find out the extent to which Limkokwing University of Creative Technology students express their need for inclusion, control and affection during collaborative learning.
- To determine the extent to which Limkokwing University of Creative Technology students want other group members to initiate their need for inclusion, control and affection during collaborative learning.
- To examine the levels of overall Interpersonal needs during collaborative learning amongst Limkokwing University of Creative Technology students.

Research questions

This paper was set out to address the following research questions:

- To what extent do Limkokwing University of Creative Technology students' express their need for inclusion, control and affection during collaborative learning?
- To what extent do Limkokwing University of Creative Technology students' want other group members to initiate their need for inclusion, control and affection during collaborative learning?

- What are the levels of Interpersonal needs during collaborative learning amongst Limkokwing University of Creative Technology students?

Research hypotheses

- H_{A1}: The students at Limkokwing University of Creative Technology significantly express their need for Inclusion, Control and Affection during collaborative learning.
- H_{A2}: The students at Limkokwing University of Creative Technology significantly want other group members to initiate their need for Inclusion, Control and Affection during collaborative learning.

Literature review

Collaborative learning

Several studies on the application of collaborative learning have focused on investigating challenges perceived by teachers other than students. Gillies and Boyle (2010) and Popov (2012) are some of the similar conducted studies which established that in a collaborative learning environment, learners encounter some challenges both socially and emotionally because they listen to different perspectives which require them to articulate and defend their views. By so doing, the learners begin to make their own unique conceptual frameworks and do not rely exclusively on the frameworks of some experts (Gillies & Boyle, 2010; Popov, 2012).

Despite the challenges that students encounter during learning, Iloanya (2014) indicated that effective teaching and learning accommodates the active involvement of learners in the learning process. In such a learning atmosphere, Iloanya (2014) pointed out that learners get motivated and also benefit from taking the responsibility for their education. Iloanya (2014) further emphasised that learning is enhanced where cooperative and collaborative learning is practiced, and that experience usually improves the quality of teaching and understanding the concepts that are learnt.

By focusing mainly on teachers or students, research reveals that the underlying problems that teachers and students face during teaching and learning towards promoting collaborative learning plus the implications of poor collaboration have not been fully understood and addressed (Ha Le et al., 2018). As such, Dommeyer (2007) pointed out that understanding the commonly mentioned problems of free-riding requires investigating the decisions that teachers implement when planning and constructing collaborative activities. Moreover, this will assist to explore how the teachers' decisions influence students' perceptions towards collaborative learning (Dommeyer, 2007).

The activities involved in collaborative learning differ extensively, but most of them revolve around students' exploration or application of the materials they study, not merely the presentation made by the teacher or how the learning materials are clarified (Koutrouba, Kariotaki & Christopoulos, 2012). Collaborative learning therefore epitomizes a significant change from the typical teacher or lecturer-centered learning in college classrooms to learner centered instruction (Koutrouba et al., 2012). Besides, in collaborative classrooms, the processes of lecturing or listening or note-taking may not be stopped completely but will be practiced with other activities which promote students active involvement in using the provided course material (Van De Pol, Volman & Beishuizen, 2011). Teachers who encourage the use of collaborative learning approaches are likely to consider themselves less as experts in transferring knowledge to students, and more as experts who coach students towards being more independent during the learning process (Van De Pol et al., 2011).

When investigating on the collaborative interactions amongst primary school children, Barron (2003) concluded that low-quality coordination amongst group members when they participated in problem-solving tasks was one of the observed challenges. In the study, it was discovered that some of the group members did not pay attention to others' opinions, interrupted them, and rejected others' alternative suggestions without any logical explanation (Barron, 2003). These behaviours limited the overall intent of teamwork and slowed down individual learning. In addition, Ross (2008) arrived at a similar conclusion that the quality of students' peer

education during collaborative sessions at primary and secondary levels holds very little shared knowledge construction and acquisition.

The other previous studies (Chiriatic & Granström, 2012; Frykedal & Chiriatic, 2011; Janssen, Erkens, Kanselaar & Jaspers, 2007) highlighted several problems that teachers encountered when applying collaborative learning, such as: Lack of paying attention by some of the group members; Lack of assertiveness in other members; Competition and continual and unconstructive arguments amongst members. Nevertheless, these studies have insufficiently provided workable solutions towards addressing the underlying problems that students experience during collaborative learning (Frykedal & Chiriatic, 2011; Janssen et al., 2007).

When students work together during learning, educators are likely to get a direct and immediate sense of how students are learning, and what experiences and ideas they bring to their work (Shimazoe & Aldrich, 2010). Therefore, the different perspectives that transpire in collaborative activities make students of various capabilities to understand what is being discussed or learnt (Shimazoe & Aldrich, 2010). Moreover, collaborative learning across teams forces the individual students to develop new connections and to find some ways of working with others (La Rocca et al., 2014). Through defending their points, reframing ideas, listening to the views of others and stating their arguments, learners engaged in collaborative learning often gain a complete understanding as a group than when learning alone (Chiriatic & Granström, 2012).

In collaborative undertakings, students certainly encounter some differences amongst themselves, and must cope with identifying and working with every circumstance they come across (Koutrouba, Kariotaki & Christopoulos, 2012). As such, they develop the abilities of tolerating others and being able to resolve some differences in a group (Freeman & Greenacre, 2010). These skills are crucial aspects of living in a community and working with people of different viewpoints (Freeman & Greenacre, 2010). Many times, the development of these values and skills is relegated to the “Student Life” side of the campus and it cultivates teamwork, community building and leadership skills which are legitimate and valuable to the teaching and learning goals (Koutrouba et al., 2012).

Fundamental Interpersonal Relations Orientation Behaviour (FIRO - B)

This is a theory of interpersonal relations which was introduced by William Schutz in 1958. The theory is based on the belief that when people are in a group, there are three main interpersonal needs that they expect to observe in a group; Affection, Control and Inclusion (Schutz, 1958). This technique was generated to measure how group members feel when it comes to inclusion, control, and affection during collaboration in order to be able to get feedback from others in a group setting (Schutz, 1958).

FIRO-B three areas of interpersonal needs

For each of the three interpersonal needs - Inclusion, Control, and Affection - the FIRO-B instrument provides measurements of how much each need is expressed or wanted by an individual.

Inclusion: This need demonstrates how much one would include other people in their lives and how much attention, contact and recognition they want from others. Inclusion is basically about how individuals relate with others in both small and large groups (Schutz, 1958).

Control: This need indicates how much influence and responsibility one wants and how much an individual wants others to lead and influence them. Control is generally about both an individual and their one-to-one relationships and behaviours when participating in group settings. It looks at how much one wants to exhibit authority, be in charge and take responsibility in groups (Schutz, 1958).

Affection: This need indicates how close and warm one is with others and how warm they want others to be with them. Affection is about the need to establish comfortable one-to-one relationships (Schutz, 1958).

Overall Interpersonal Needs

The indicator of the Overall Interpersonal Needs, is the total score of all the six individual needs ($eI + wI + eC + wC + eA + wA$) which are each scored from (0-9), and the overall maximum score for all the needs is $(9 \times 6) = 54$. The FIRO-Results represent the overall strength of one's interpersonal needs; it shows how much an

individual believes that other people and human interactions can them to attain their personal goals and achieve personal satisfaction.

Scoring and interpretation of the Fundamental Interpersonal Relationship Orientation- Behaviour (FIRO-B) model results

This section presents guidelines on how to score and interpret the FIRO-B results when evaluating the influence of interpersonal needs on collaborative learning efforts during participation in group assignments and projects amongst Limkokwing University of Creative Technology students in Botswana.

Table 1

Scoring the FIRO- B Needs asa Single Aspect

Scores	Corresponding Behaviors
7 - 9 : HIGH	This behaviour is very characteristic of oneself (in most situations/ in most groups)
4 - 6 : MEDIUM	The behaviours are noticeable characteristic (some of the times /in certain groups)
0 - 3 : LOW	One uses this behavior infrequently and or with a few selectedgroups.

Total Expressed and Total Wanted Scores

The total expressed scores shows how much an individual would usually like to initiate action when relating to others in a group setting and the total wanted scores indicate how much an individual would normally prefer that others take the initiative and lead. The scoring of the Total Expressed and Total Wanted scores range from (0 - 27) as depicted in Table 2.

Table 2

Interpretation of Total Expressed and Total Wanted Scores

Scores	Category	Interpretation
0 - 7	low	For Expressed: An individual usually do not initiate activities with others. For Wanted: An individual usually do not want others to initiate activities.
8 - 19	medium	For Expressed: Sometimes one initiates activities with others, sometimes one doesn't. For Wanted: Sometimes individual wants others to initiate activities with them, sometimes they don't.
20 - 27	high	For Expressed: An individual usually initiates activities with others. For Wanted: An individual usually like others to initiate activities with them.

The interpretation of the Total Needs is calculated based on the (Total of Expressed Needs plus the Total of Wanted Needs). These scores range from 0-54 and are categorised as indicated in Table 3.

Table 3

Interpretation of Total Need Scores (Total Expressed and Total Wanted Scores)

Total need score	Rating	Meaning
0 - 15	low	Interaction with others in all areas of Inclusion, Control and Affection is not likely to be a strongly felt need.
16 - 26	Medium - low	Interaction with others in all the areas of Inclusion, Control and Affection may appeal to one on a selective basis.
27 - 38	Medium high	An individual generally finds that interacting with other people in all areas of Inclusion, Control and Affection is a source of satisfaction and that their interpersonal relationships help them attain the goals they want to reach.
39 - 54	high	One probably enjoys engaging frequently with others in all areas of Inclusion, Control and Affection.

Research methodology

This paper used the quantitative research approach to evaluate the influence of interpersonal needs on collaborative learning efforts during participation in group assignments and projects amongst Limkokwing University of Creative Technology students in Botswana. The FIRO-B questionnaire, which is focused on three basic human needs: Inclusion, Control and Affection was used for this study. Random sampling was used to select **50** students who participated in the study. All the questionnaires were returned and used for data analysis.

Data Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation

Data was analysed using SPSS and descriptive statistics (Mean and Standard Deviation) were used to analyse interpret results. The analysis and the interpretation of the results were based on the findings obtained from the data collected using the questionnaire instrument. A total of **50** copies of questionnaires were administered; out of which all were returned. The hypotheses were tested as follows:

H₀₁: Limkokwing University of Creative Technology students' do not significantly express their need for Inclusion, Control and Affection during collaborative learning.

The overall mean (M = 20.34, SD = 5.13) of the three aspects indicate that students at Limkokwing University of Creative Technology usually initiate activities with others most of the time during collaborative learning. These results led to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

Table 4

Analysis of Limkokwing University of Creative Technology students Expressed Inclusion, Control and Affection During Collaborative Learning

Variables	N	Total expressed = (eI + eC + eA)	Mean	SD
EXPRESSED_INCLUSION	50	347	6.94	1.78
EXPRESSED_CONTROL	50	322	6.44	1.80
EXPRESSED_AFFECTION	50	348	6.96	1.55
Total		1017	20.34	5.13

Table 4 shows that students' need for expressed affection has statistically high mean (M = 6.96, SD = 1.55) than their need for Expressed Inclusion (M = 6.94, SD = 1.78) and Expressed Control at (M = 6.44, SD = 1.80). These results indicate that Limkokwing University of Creative Technology students express medium levels (4-6) on their needs for Wanted Inclusion, Control and Affection during collaborative learning.

H₀₂: Limkokwing University of Creative Technology students' do not significantly want other group members to initiate their need for Inclusion, Control and Affection during collaborative learning.

The overall mean (M = 19.54, SD = 4.84) of the three aspects indicate that Limkokwing University of Creative Technology students allow each other to initiate activities during collaborative learning, but this does not happen most of the time, thus the results led to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

Table 5

Analysis of Limkokwing University Students' Wanted Inclusion, Control and Affection during Collaborative Learning

Variables	N	Total wanted = (wI + wC + wA)	Mean	SD
WANTED_INCLUSION	50	335	6.70	1.555
WANTED_CONTROL	50	290	5.80	1.604
WANTED_AFFECTION	50	352	7.04	1.678
Total		977	19.54	4.837

Table 5 shows that students' need for wanted affection is statistically significant at ($M = 7.04$, $SD = 1.68$) and falls within the high (7 - 9) FIRO-B scoring range, as compared to Wanted Inclusion ($M = 6.70$, $SD = 1.56$) and Wanted Control ($M = 5.80$, $SD = 1.60$) which fall within the medium (4 - 6) FIRO-B scoring range. These results indicate that students at Limkokwing University of Creative Technology express high levels of wanted affection during group collaboration in most situations and most groups, therefore, implying that students usually like others to initiate activities amongst group participants.

Summary and conclusion

This study investigated on the influence of interpersonal needs on collaborative learning efforts during participation in group assignments and projects amongst Limkokwing University students in Botswana. This was conducted in order to understand students' point of view towards collaborative learning so as to enhance ways in which lecturers at the university plan group assignments and other collaborative activities.

The results of the study showed that students at Limkokwing University of Creative Technology have high levels of interpersonal needs. The total needs (Total Expressed + Total Wanted) = ($M = 20.34 + M = 19.54$) = 39.88. The total needs score (39.88) falls within the high range of the FIRO-B scale (39 - 54). On the other hand, this study also revealed some of the factors that limited collaborative efforts by students which are mostly attributed to lack of collaborative skills and limited ability to take leadership roles in group settings. Barron (2003) discovered that for teams to be effective during collaboration there is need for educators to articulate the integration between social goals, discourse practices and how knowledge building processes lead to knowledge construction and acquisition during teaching and learning.

Recommendations

- Lecturers at Limkokwing University of Creative Technology should :
 - Be equipped with some strategies to set clear cognitive and collaborative goals in the curriculum in order to support collaborative skills development amongst learners.
 - Consider using student-workload matrix for assessing group assignments, and distribute the workload for each individual member that would build on the main component of the group task.
 - Consider using different strategies, like the Jigsaw technique. This involves subdividing an assignment into subtasks, where individuals are expected to research or complete their assigned area.
 - Ensure that students learn together by implementing the pre-test and post-test assessment strategies.
 - Design assignments that create opportunities for varied interpretations and focused on enhancing problem-solving and critical thinking skills amongst learners.
 - Design assignments that are current and include a range of talents, backgrounds, learning styles, ideas, and experiences by students.
- Students should be encouraged to join sporting clubs, debate clubs and social networks in order for them to build on their social skills, communication skills, leadership skills and sense of belonging.
- Universities in Botswana should introduce in their curriculum, common modules that teach students about social skills, and collaboration skills so that students are able to take initiative, control and manage their teams.

Recommendation for future research

The following research topics can be conducted as directed by the findings of this study:

- The Impact of Interpersonal Needs on Collaborative Learning Efforts during Participation in Group Assignments amongst Students with Learning Disabilities.
- The Impact of Interpersonal Needs on Work Collaboration amongst University Staff in Botswana.

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